

JHEAA

ISSN: 3032-1123

<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.722>**APPLICATION OF AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENT IN
LEARNING POETRY TEXTS IN JUNIOR HIGH
SCHOOL STUDENTS****Niken Aprilla¹, Dina Fitria Handayani²**^{1,2} Adzka University Indonesian Language Educationnikenapri01@gmail.com

Received: May 22, 2024; Accepted: June 29, 2024; Published: Jul 08, 2024;

Abstract: This research aims to investigate the application of authentic assessment in teaching poetry texts at the secondary level (SMP) and the challenges faced by Indonesian language teachers with errors. In this process, Education is an effort to change a person's attitudes and behavior towards maturity through training and guidance. The 2013 curriculum requires students to be more active and inclusive in the learning process through continuous assessment which includes cognitive, attitude and ability aspects. However, practice in this area places more emphasis on cognitive aspects, and full-scale assessments are required to assess students' overall abilities. This research uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. Data was collected through interviews, observation and recording with Indonesian language teachers. Triangulation techniques are used to test the validity of the data. Data analysis was carried out descriptively to obtain an in-depth understanding of the implementation of authentic assessment and the obstacles teachers face in teaching poetry texts.

Keywords: Authentic Assessment, Poetry, Study

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) licenses

Introduction

Education is an effort to change the attitudes and behavior of individuals or groups to become more mature through training and guidance. This is the opinion of Rahmat and Abdillah (2019) that education is the development of potential that adults consciously and deliberately give to students to achieve goals and realize the tasks of independent life. Students who are the subject of the learning process are independent of their teachers and cannot be separated. Basically, the 2013 Curriculum requires students to be more proactive, and its implementation is truly inclusive of character and abilities, involves continuous assessment, and is comprehensive and continuously clarifies various aspects of their own desires. The evaluation process is an activity that ranges from the extent of the learning process to the degree of success or failure in learning achieved by the students themselves. In the opinion of Pangesti & Sufanti (2020), learning evaluation can be used to monitor the activity process of various students and can be used as information when evaluating students.

To obtain general learning processes and outcomes, it is necessary to assess attitudes, abilities, knowledge and skills. In fact, it has been proven in the field that learning processes and outcomes, especially student assessments, generally only emphasize cognitive or knowledge aspects. This will only impress students by memorizing the daily test questions

that will appear later in the test. Therefore, an authentic evaluation was held, namely a type of process evaluation and learning outcomes as an effort to achieve this. Setting learning goals and supporting improving the quality of education. The results of this assessment can provide a real picture and can be used to evaluate all abilities, both intellectual performance and student practice, especially in junior high school Indonesian language classes.

In secondary schools there are writing skills that train students to be creative. Writing is an activity of giving, conveying ideas and thoughts through symbols that can be used as works such as poetry. After the process and examination of the results, an appropriate evaluation or assessment must be carried out so that it can influence student learning outcomes in the field of Indonesian language education, especially the results of poetry text material. Every Indonesian language teacher teaches students and implements the 2013 curriculum which aims to assess aspects of attitude, knowledge and skills.

However, in its application, not a few teachers have difficulty doing it. Implementation of authentic assessments of student learning outcomes. For this reason, researchers studied in depth the implementation of authentic assessment and the obstacles experienced by teachers in the teaching process, especially poetry text material. Based on the background above, the problem formulation in this research is How to apply authentic assessment in learning poetry texts. The aim of this research is to find out how to apply authentic assessment in learning poetry texts for junior high school students, to find out the obstacles encountered by Indonesian language subject teachers in implementing authentic assessment in learning poetry texts.

Methods

This research uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. Bogdan and Taylor (in Moleong 2013: 4) Qualitative research is a procedure or research stage that produces descriptive data in the form of people's written and spoken words and observable behavior. This research data was collected from Indonesian language teachers in the form of interviews, learning tools, lesson plans, and assessments of attitudes, knowledge and skills. The data source for this research is language teachers. Data collection techniques were carried out. Involves observation, interviews, and documentation. The testing technique used to determine the validity of the data in this research is triangulation. Data analysis was carried out. Use descriptive analysis techniques. Nasution, Sugiyono (2017) stated that analysis begins with formulating and explaining the problem before going into the field and continues until the research results are documented.

Results and Discussion

Based on interviews with several teachers and school principals, it seems that authentic assessment has not been implemented properly and optimally. This is in line with research by Wahyuni (2010: 71) showing that authentic assessment has not been implemented correctly and optimally in schools. In general, the assessment system is unable to accurately describe student abilities, and students are unable to master material that is appropriate to the real world.

Authentic assessment is an assessment that guides students in expressing their knowledge and ideas combined with completing assignments/exercises related to the required competencies and skills (Ridwan, 2016: 23). Amelia et al (2020) stated that authentic evaluation evaluates participants regarding the process and results using various assessment tools that are adapted to competency requirements, namely competency standards, core competencies (AI), and basic competencies (KD). The aim of authentic assessment is to meaningfully measure student attitudes. My knowledge and skills have increased significantly (Hascan, 2021).

In other words, authentic assessment is a performance evaluation that aims to show what students have learned and what skills they have acquired through the learning process. Of course, students will perform better if they themselves understand what is required regarding the content presented. According to the Notification of the Minister of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology Number 66 of 2013, a comprehensive evaluation is an evaluation carried out to thoroughly assess the input, process and output of learning.

Types of authentic assessment can be divided into assessments of attitudes, knowledge and skills.

- a. Majid Attitude Assessment (2017) Assessment of learning outcomes including attitude abilities is an important activity to measure student attitudes as a result of a learning program. Attitude measurements that teachers must complete include behavioral observations, individual/self-assessments, peer assessments, and personal reports (diaries).
- b. Knowledge Assessment Assessment of the achievement of knowledge competency is part of educational assessment. In all subjects in secondary school, the core knowledge competencies that students must have are understanding factual, conceptual and procedural knowledge (Majid, 2017).
- c. Competency assessment is an assessment that determines the extent to which students apply skills as a result of knowledge obtained during learning and demonstrate these skills through student products and performance. The skills themselves are part of subsequent thinking and action (Secondary School Development Authority, 2017). The competency aspect assessment technique uses the following methods: practice assessment, product assessment, project assessment, portfolio assessment.

Skills assessment is carried out to provide an overview of core competencies, including more complex competencies, so that the type of assessment is in the form of practice and project or portfolio work products. Students demonstrate skills in the form of actions and products, and teachers evaluate them using rubrics. For example, basic competence expresses the content of poetry performed live or via recording. The types of evaluation are poetry reading exercises, project reports based on discussion results, and portfolios.

Authentic Assessment Planning in Poetry Texts

Before carrying out a full-scale assessment, the teacher first creates an assessment plan that is in accordance with the learning plan to ensure the assessment is carried out appropriately. Researchers asked several questions related to the authentic teacher evaluation planning process in the RPP.

G1: The RPP also establishes a comprehensive assessment that assesses attitudes through observation. I saw their attitude firsthand. Knowledge of poetry texts is reviewed from written exams and performance skills, especially performance skills in front of the class.

G2: A comprehensive assessment plan is carried out by creating a Learning Performance Plan (RPP) for Core Competencies (KI) and Basic Competencies (KD) and setting Minimum Completeness Standards (KKM) for each material. Authentic assessment assesses three aspects of learning: abilities, attitudes, knowledge, and skills. And in lyric text material, all these aspects are looked at and evaluated when studying lyric text material.

Next, learn how teachers design assessment tools. Assessment tools include existing qualifications, namely a description or presentation of the skills that will be assessed to students. This is based on the results of interviews with informants, observations and document analysis. This preparation is prepared in a RPP with several elements contained in the RPP such as objectives, indicators, questions and evaluation, and is carried out with practical consideration of students' attitudes, knowledge and skills. Fulfill the requirements of the 2013 Curriculum at the design stage through creating learning plans and determining assessments.

Barriers to Implementing Authentic Assessments

In the teaching and learning process there may be obstacles in its implementation. Barriers to implementing authentic assessment.

G1: There are a lot of serious assessment points and they all need to be evaluated, so it is difficult to implement them all. That's right.

G2: The obstacles I encounter are that students are honest when assessing, sometimes they don't know whether students are honest, and there is a lack of parental support to get good behavior from students.

For every aspect of authentic assessment that needs to be assessed in terms of attitudes, knowledge and skills, teachers have difficulty carrying it out, especially in poetry text material, even though the assessment is authentic. This is mandatory in the 2013 curriculum. Ridwan (2016), based on the results of interviews and supported by documentary data and observations, describes the difficulties that teachers usually face when assessing student attitudes, especially during evaluations. First, teachers still do not understand authentic assessment due to a lack of training and socialization in the 2013 curriculum. Second, teachers have difficulty identifying assessment results, especially when assessing student attitudes. Establishing criteria for considering and evaluating

students in the real world is confounded by multiple evaluation aspects and metrics. Third, lack of parental support. Assessment of students' attitudes is not optimal only in the school environment, but must be optimized based on students' attitudes at home and in the community. Fourth, there is a lack of time to carry out competency assessments, because assessing competency aspects takes longer

Conclusion

Interviews and surveys show that the implementation of authentic assessment in schools is still less than optimal. Authentic assessment aims to comprehensively measure students' abilities in attitudes, knowledge and skills related to the real world. Even though the theory is good, in practice there are various obstacles. Attitude assessments require teachers to observe student behavior, which is often difficult to do consistently. Knowledge assessments measure students' factual, conceptual, and procedural understanding, and skills assessments assess students' ability to apply knowledge through practice, products, projects, and portfolios. The main obstacles in implementing a comprehensive assessment include the large number of assessment components that must be assessed, the difficulty of measuring student honesty, and the lack of parental support. In addition, due to the lack of training and socialization in the 2013 Curriculum, teachers often lack understanding of authentic assessment. Another challenge is establishing consistent evaluation criteria and limited time to conduct a comprehensive evaluation. Authentic assessment is expected to provide a more accurate picture of student abilities, but its implementation still requires a lot of improvement and support to be successful.

References

- [1].Adhi, MK (2015). Authentic assessment in literature learning: a literature review. *Literacy*, 27(2), 217-227.
- [2].Hascan. 2021. Assessment Implementation. Authentic at Primary, Middle and Higher Education in Indonesia. *Journal of Nonformal Education*. 2(1): 231-240
- [3].Pangesti, Cita RN & Sufanti, M. (2020). Online Learning Assessment of Poetry Texts for Indonesian Language Subjects during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Pena: Journal of Language and Literature Education*. 10(2): 72-88.
- [4].Putri, MS, Purba, A., & Rasdawita, R. (2022). Implementation of Authentic Assessment of Poetry Texts for Class VIII Middle School, Alam Barajo District, Jambi City, FY 2021/2022. *Literacy: Journal of Indonesian Language and Literature and Learning*, 6(2), 251-258.
- [5]. Rahmat, H & Abdillah. 2019, IMU Education "Concept. Theory and Applications". Medan: LPPPI.